

Mixed Ligand Complexes with Sulphur Donor Ligands and Thiocyanato-N/Cyanato-N

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In continuation of our earlier work¹ on transition metal complexes of heterocyclic Schiff bases, we report here the synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) and copper(II) with [(methylthiophen-2-yl)methylene]hydrazono-carbothioamide (**1**, MTHT) and hydrazinecarbothioamide (**2**, HT) and thiocyanato-N (SCN)/cyanato-N (OCN).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, and insoluble in water and other common organic solvents such as methanol and ethanol but readily soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. The molar conductivity values of the complexes in DMF are in the range 6–12 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-electrolytic nature².

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compl./ (Colour)	Analysis % : (Found/(Calcd.))		
	C	H	N
Co(HT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (Green)	14.39 (13.44)	2.83 2.50	32.77 31.37
Co(MTHT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (Green)	35.60 (35.50)	4.32 3.14	19.01 19.54
Co(HT) ₂ (OCN) ₂ (Brown)	14.02 (14.76)	2.90 3.07	33.03 34.46
Co(MTHT) ₂ (OCN) ₂ (Green)	35.02 (35.62)	2.76 2.96	20.02 20.17
Cu(HT) ₂ (OCN) ₂ (Yellow)	12.57 (13.29)	3.25 2.76	30.20 30.97
Cu(MTHT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ (Yellow)	32.69 (33.35)	2.87 2.78	19.29 19.45
Cu(HT) ₂ (OCN) ₂ (Brown)	13.96 (14.56)	2.98 3.03	34.02 33.98
Cu(MTHT) ₂ (OCN) ₂ (Green)	34.90 (35.32)	3.00 2.94	19.90 20.60

The magnetic moments of [Co(HT)₂(SCN)₂] and [Co(HT)₂(OCN)₂] are found to be 4.8 and 5.0 B.M., suggesting their high-spin octahedral structure³. The values of 1.7 and 1.6 B.M. for [Co(MTHT)₂(SCN)₂] and [Co(MTHT)₂(OCN)₂] complexes are in favour of low-spin octahedral structure. The values of magnetic moment of the copper complexes are 1.82–2.10 B.M., normally observed for copper(II) complexes.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes are dominated by charge transfer bands tailed into visible regions. However, two distinct bands observed at 15 330–16 130 and 25 847–27 030 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the cobalt complexes are attributable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transitions respectively, which suggest an octahedral structure⁴. The ν_1 band is not observed in the spectra of the cobalt complexes. In the spectra of the copper complexes, the bands at 17 390–17 940 cm^{-1} are assignable to d-d transitions.

The IR spectrum of HT shows bands at 3 372 and 3 329 cm^{-1} assignable to $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ stretching vibration of amino and imino groups respectively. The former band shifted ($\Delta = \sim 80 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) towards lower wavenumber suggesting the participation of amino group in coordination. A strong ligand HT band observed at 1 268 cm^{-1} (C=S) ($\Delta = \sim 50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) towards lower wavenumber in all the complexes indicating the involvement of thioketo sulphur⁵ in coordination.

The high frequency bands in the spectra of MTHT observed at 3 408 and 3 242 cm^{-1} are assigned to amino and imino groups. These bands are not affected in the spectra of the metal complexes, indicating the non-participation of terminal amino group in coordination. A strong ligand MTHT band at 1 606 cm^{-1} (C=N)⁶ shifted ($\Delta = \sim 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted towards lower wavenumber in the spectra of all the complexes, suggesting the involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. Strong and sharp ligand MTHT bands at 1 286 cm^{-1} (C=S) of MTHT is assigned to $\nu(\text{C=S})$ stretching vibration. ($\Delta = \sim 40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) towards lower wavenumber suggesting the participation of thioketo sulphur in coordination. Thiophene ring vibration ligand band (1 531 cm^{-1}) is not affected in spectra of all the complexes, suggesting the non-participation of ring sulphur in coordination. The spectrum of SCN ligands shows bands at 2 303 (C–N) and 748 cm^{-1} (C–S). In the spectra of the complexes containing SCN the former band shifted ($\Delta =$

$\sim 80\text{ cm}^{-1}$) towards higher wavenumber, which suggests that SCN ligand is binding the metal ion through nitrogen⁷. Ir spectra of OCN complexes, similarly support OCN ligand binding through nitrogen donor atom.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

[Methylthiophen-2-yl]methylene]hydrazonocarbothioamide : A mixture of equimolar amounts of 2-acetylthiophene and thiosemicarbazide (2) in ethanol containing a few drops of conc. HCl was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled to yield a light yellow coloured solid (45%), m.p. 152–54° (Found : C, 40.95; H, 4.56; N, 19.97. $\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{S}_2$ calcd. for : C, 42.22; H, 4.52; N, 21.10%); δ (CDCl_3) 8.94 (1H, s, imino), 6.72 (2H, s, amino), 7.04 (1H, dd, thiophene-5), 2.38 (3H, s, CH_3).

Synthesis of complexes : To a hot solution of MTHT or HT (0.01 mol) and SCN or OCN (0.01 mol), requisite quantity of the metal salt (0.05 mol) dissolved in minimum amount of water was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6–8 h under inert N_2 -atmosphere. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with cold methanol and hot water, and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

Molar conductivity, magnetic susceptibility, electronic, ir and ^1H nmr spectra were measured as described earlier⁸.

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References

1. K. H. REDDY and Y. LINGAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1994, **33**, 919; S. RAO and K. H. REDDY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 681; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 532.
2. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
3. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1980.
4. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
5. S. K. SAHANI and V. B. RANA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 271; J. JENSEN and P. M. NIELSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1996, **20**, 597.
6. M. K. DUTT and M. C. CHAKDER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 2303.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 2nd. ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1972, p. 188.
8. A. KRISHNA, K. H. REDDY and D. V. REDDY, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1990, **173**, 13; K. H. REDDY, G. KRISHNAIAH and Y. SREENIVASULU, *Polyhedron*, 1991, **10**, 2785.